

FORMATION OF THE MOTIVATIONAL SPHERE OF MORAL QUALITIES OF STUDENTS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TEACHING THE HUMANITIES)

Rakhimova Iroda Ravshanovna

Teacher at Samarkand state architecture and civil engineering university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880255>

Abstract. *The paper presents the results of a study devoted to identifying the features of the motivational sphere of higher school students in different areas of professional training.*

Keywords: *motivation, inspiration, results, students, motivational sphere.*

The motivational sphere of a person is a system of factors, conditions and means, motives, needs, attitudes, and other social and psychological phenomena that significantly affect its development and formation. In modern conditions of social development, the problem of developing the motivational sphere of a modern student's personality becomes particularly relevant. The very problem of studying the motivational sphere of a student's personality in psychological science is one of the most popular. This is due to the fact that rethinking one's place in society, re-evaluating the significance of many value orientations, and taking responsibility for the results of life are hidden in the individual's motives and require management. In psychological and pedagogical science, a personality-oriented approach is associated with a deep interest in the motivational sphere of students' personality as subjects of educational relations, factors, conditions and means of activating its development in them context of professional formation.

Motivation is the basis of any activity, including educational. Scientists dealing with the problem of motivation of educational activity emphasize the great importance of its development and preservation. It is educational motivation that guarantees the formation of cognitive activity, the development of thinking, and the acquisition of knowledge necessary for the successful professional activity of personality. The basis of successful educational and then professional activities is a high level of motivation for this type of activity. However, at present, when there is a huge amount of information provided by such sources as the media, the Internet, and social networks, it is very difficult to motivate a student to systematic study, systematic work with educational literature, and effective use knowledge in the training process.

It should be noted that while studying at the higher educational institution, the psychological foundation of the professional activity of the future specialist is formed. Mastering a profession is a rather long and complex process that has internal patterns and qualitatively peculiar stages. Of particular importance in the development of a person as a professional is the period of development of educational and professional activities. In the motivation of students' educational and professional activities, a distinctive feature is that the educational and professional components of motivation are constantly combined with each other. The strength of motivation and its structure has a significant impact on the success of students' educational and professional activities.

Students in different areas of professional training revealed the specific of the manifestation of the motivational sphere. In a group of students of humanitarian areas of professional training, satisfaction with their professional decision (choosing a profession, place of study, and place of

work), the opportunity to benefit society with their work, and achieving good results will be important for maintaining high motivation. They also have a high level of emotional involvement (life optimism, emotional balance and tolerance of failures), and the development of mental and physical abilities to match the chosen profession or chosen work. A high desire to get satisfaction from their work and be original in their work, a desire to support social progress with their work, to strive to improve their moral appearance, develop moral qualities, to master special knowledge, to know the content of a particular work, to get opportunities for creativity, will occupy one of the first places.

In a group of students of technical areas of professional training, satisfaction with their professional decision (choosing a profession, place of study, and place of work), the ability to benefit society with their work, and achieving good results will also be important for maintaining high motivation. They also have a high level of emotional involvement (life optimism, emotional balance, and tolerance for failure), and the development of mental and physical abilities to match the chosen profession or work. The high desire to get satisfaction from their activities and be original in their work, the desire to support social progress with their work, to strive to improve their moral image, develop moral qualities, to master special knowledge, knowledge of the content of a particular work, to get opportunities for creativity, will occupy one of the first places. But in addition, students of technical areas of professional training have priority awareness of the chosen profession and the world of the profession as a whole, the ability to plan their professional life and the ability to independently make important professional decisions. With high emotional involvement, students of technical areas of professional training practically do not have the fear of being wrong or making a mistake, receiving criticism and punishment for mistakes. The results of the comparative study allow us to note that for students of humanitarian areas of professional training, the motivation for success is more important than for students of technical areas of professional training; for students of technical areas of professional training, awareness about the chosen profession prevails in comparison with humanitarian areas of professional training.

REFERENCES

1. E.J. Zarubko, Internet journal “World of science. Pedagogy and psychology” 4, 6 (2018) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24412/Fg6KWdIVNg4>
2. N.N. Vasyagina, E.L. Afanasenkova, J.A. Vedyashkina, S.A. Vasyagina, N.V. Abramovskih, The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS PSYRGGU LXIV, 740 – 747 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.07.96>